

EXPLORING THE NEXUS: STREET HARASSMENT, DECISION REGRET, AND POST-TRAUMATIC GROWTH AMONG YOUNG WOMEN

Javeria Yaqoob^{*1}, Dr. Beenish Mubeen², Dr. Shahnila Tariq³

^{*1,2,3}department of Applied Psychology School of Professional Psychology University of Management And Technology, Lahore

^{*1}Javeria.yaqoob10@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *
Javeria Yaqoob

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationships between street harassment, decision regret and post-traumatic growth among young women. It aims to determine whether these variables interact with and predict post-traumatic growth. Utilizing a correlational research design, the sample of 250 young women aged 19 to 35 (M = 23.37, SD = 4.05), was selected through non-probability purposive sampling. The study utilized the Mexican Sexual Street Harassment questionnaire (MSSHQ), the Decision Regret Scale (DRS) and the Post-Traumatic Growth Inventory (PTGI) to measure the relevant variables. The analysis revealed significant positive relations among street harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth. Additionally, street harassment and decision regret were significant predictors of post-traumatic growth. The findings reveal that although street harassment and decision regret are negative experiences, distress and reflection triggered by such experiences can lead to significant positive psychological growth. The novel combination of variables in this study points to a gap in the previous literature. It also provides a new perspective for young women facing street harassment, demonstrating that despite the trauma and its effects, they can achieve significant positive psychological growth. This understanding can offer hope and encourage personal strength among those affected.

Keywords: street harassment, young women victims, trauma, decision regret, post-traumatic growth, positive growth

INTRODUCTION

On every street corner, the echoes of harassment linger, painting a somber picture of the pervasive issue that affects countless young women worldwide. Streets are shadowed by the constant threat of street harassment, creating an environment of fear and intimidation for women. Crimes against one woman can terrorize an entire community, illustrating the profound impact of such behavior. Confronting this unsettling truth is crucial because street harassment can become normalized, and deeply embedded in societal norms because societal

institutes such as media and family display young women as objects of pleasure. This cultural acceptance and excess personal encounters leads many women to internalize the harassment, question their decisions, and believing that street harassment is an unavoidable aspect of their public life. This study investigates the understudied issue of street harassment and provide light on the potential for growth that might arise from such difficult experiences by investigating the psychological effects and connection between the trauma and positive

growth.

Street Harassment

Harassment on the streets occurs when an unknown person approaches a stranger in an inappropriate way and treats the victim badly such as causing them to feel annoyed, angered, embarrassed, afraid, humiliated, or dread because of their appearance, sexual orientation, or expression of that gender (Kearl, 2010). The behaviors associated with street harassment are less severe actions, including smooching noises, horn honking, or whistling, to more severe actions, including threats, stalking, pinching and frottage (Macmillan et al., 2000). These behaviors impose unwanted interactions on women in various public spaces, including shopping malls, public transportation, parks. Consequently, the independence and freedom of young women can be severely compromised, limiting their ability to navigate public spaces without fear or anxiety (Hutson & Krueger, 2019). There are many types of harassment such as Verbal or Non-verbal which encompasses irritated noises, gestures, and remarks of a vulgar nature Gloria et al., 2022. Although often dismissed as harmless or trivial, these behaviors can significantly impact the victim's sense of safety and self-worth. Moreover, Physical harassment involves unwanted touching, brushing, or grazing against a person's body in a sexual manner (Gloria et al., 2022). lastly, Explicit Sexual Harassment includes more intimidating behaviors, such as cornering, chasing someone, exhibitionism, or public masturbation (Gloria et al., 2022). Street harassment has a disastrous impact on the psychological, emotional, and physical well-being of the victims, causing discomfort, fear, and a sense of threat (Hutson & Krueger, 2018). Despite the various challenges faced due to street harassment, many women choose to remain silent if such a thing happens to them. This silence is mostly due to fear of escalating the situation or being humiliated, particularly in societies where a woman's reputation is tied to her honor such as, societies like Pakistan where women often experience harassment and are frequently blamed for it, ultimately discouraging victims from reporting incidents (Gutek et al., 1985-1997).

To cope with or avoid street harassment, women may adopt various behavioral strategies,

significantly altering their daily routines and habits. These adjustments aim to mitigate the ongoing regret and again risk of harassment. (Calogero et al., 2021; Kearl, 2014).

Decision Regret

Decision-making is the cognitive process of evaluating and contemplating many options and then choosing the one considered most effective in achieving one or more goals or objectives. Decision-making operations are essential components of human thinking and have a crucial influence on many aspects of life, such as interpersonal and social decisions in daily life. If the consequences of a decision turn out to be negative, the feeling of regret can linger and affect future decision-making (Connolly et al., 2013).

Regret is linked to the idea of a mistake made or an opportunity missed, provoking the desire to correct and resolve the situation (Inman & Zeelenberg, 2002; Nicolao, 2002; Tsiros & Mittal, 2000). It is a self-focused negative emotion about something that has happened or been done, arising from doing or not doing something believed should or should not have been done (Seta et al., 2008). The experience of these feelings entails recognizing one's responsibility in current situations and often includes self-blame (Roese & Summerville, 2005).

Replay a situation in mind and wishing a different choice had been made is a common experience, leading to self-blame and "what if" scenarios, known as decision regret. The experience of regret is not limited to adverse outcomes resulting from incorrect or illogical choices or behaviors but also extends to situations where there exists a readily available counterfactual alternative to one's actions, especially in situations where a better outcome was narrowly missed (Miller & Taylor, 1995).

When an individual goes through the experience of regret, they may recriminate themselves and seek actions to diminish the negative effects of the decision that was made.

The first component of regret involves the analysis of one's decision regarding the comparison between actual outcomes and counterfactual outcomes. This process entails considering what could have happened if a different decision had been made, often leading to the conclusion that a potential alternate option might have resulted in a beneficial

outcome. Feelings of regret become more intensified when a person thinks and realizes or points out missed opportunities that give better outcomes after the negative outcome comes (Kahneman & Tversky, 1984). Another component of regret is characterized by thoughts of regret and self-blaming behaviors, in addition to personal judgment regarding the quality of the decisions. When individuals attribute the negative outcome of a decision to their own action or actions, they are likely to experience stronger regret (Roese & Summerville, 2005). This self-blame can lead to a cycle of negative emotions, where individuals continuously replay their decisions and criticize themselves for perceived mistakes (Sugden, 1985). Regret may result in a variety of unpleasant emotional effects, including guilt, shame, and anger. It can also impair decision-making abilities, leading to rumination and avoidance of future choices (Zeelenberg et al., 2000). On the flip side, regret can be a powerful motivator for personal growth. It can stimulate learning from mistakes, fostering resilience and adaptability (McCormack & Uprichard, 2018). Moreover, reflecting on past decisions can lead to deeper self-awareness and understanding of personal values (Tsiros & Mittal, 2000).

Regret, often viewed as a purely negative emotion, can serve as a catalyst for positive personal growth. When individuals reflect on past decisions and acknowledge their mistakes, they create opportunities for learning and self-improvement. This process of self-reflection can foster resilience and adaptability, helping individuals make better decisions in the future (Zeelenberg et al., 2000).

Additionally, understanding the sources and consequences of regret can lead to deeper self-awareness and alignment with personal values. By embracing regret as a valuable feedback mechanism, individuals can convert those negative encounters into potent catalysts for personal development and positive (McCormack & Uprichard, 2018).

Post-Traumatic Growth

The concept of "trauma" embraces a wide range of conditions, including physical as well as psychological injuries. Trauma survivors often face significant challenges, including major impairments in self-care, difficulties in forming

healthy interactions, relationship building, disruptions in memories, sense of self, and cognition (Zetterberg, 2010). Encountering trauma is a nearly unavoidable aspect of life and generally falls beyond our control. Despite these severe impacts, positive psychology theorists argue that trauma can also lead to positive and transformative effects. They suggest that acknowledging the potential benefits of trauma is crucial (Seligman, 2008). It highlights a global shift towards recognizing how individuals who undergo harm, mishaps, death loss, serious medical conditions, violence, assault, and other horrific incidents frequently describe experiencing constructive transformations in their lives (Powell et al., 2003; Taku et al., 2014; Xu & Liao, 2011).

Psychologists Richard Tedeschi and Lawrence Calhoun discovered the concept of "post-traumatic growth" during the 1990s. Defined as the phenomenon of experiencing beneficial change as a result from struggling with extremely difficult life crises, post-traumatic growth (PTG) aligns with positive psychology's perspective that both positive and negative life experiences contribute to personal flourishing.

Positive Aspects of Post-traumatic growth embraces various constructive transformations people feel or experience after facing trauma. These transformations can manifest in activities such as writing books, finding spiritual meaning, starting charities, and more (Scully, 2023). Often, post-traumatic growth improves the perceptions of oneself, relationships with others, and an individual's view of life.

Individuals may undergo heightened awareness of themselves, reinforced self-assurance, a more receptive disposition towards other people, an amplified gratitude for life, and a discovery of novel prospects (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004).

On the other hand negative aspects undoubtedly impact individuals, and the presence of these challenges can facilitate personal growth. Post-traumatic growth refers to the "positive psychological developments that occur as a consequence of facing and overcoming extremely difficult life circumstances," emphasizing that growth is intricately linked to overcoming adversity (Calhoun & Tedeschi, 2004). It is crucial to understand that the development of post-traumatic growth means it does not reduce the negative consequences of trauma. On the

contrary, it is the existence of these adverse effects that enable positive growth in trauma survivors. This means that the struggle with trauma is integral to the process of growth, highlighting that post-traumatic growth is a response to, rather than a negation of, the difficulties faced. This perspective emphasizes that such development takes place alongside, and as an outcome of overcoming trauma. It is not an immediate process; it requires significant time, energy, and internal motivation (Calhoun & Tedeschi, 2004). For individuals already grappling with challenges, even routine events may feel overwhelming and exacerbate distress. Nevertheless, some individuals find that they emerge stronger from these tough experiences.

The Five Areas of Growth

Relating with Others. It captures deepened relationships and increased appreciation of social support that individuals often experience after encountering a potentially traumatic event (PTE). Following the trauma experience, individuals may become more emotionally connected within their social networks, experiencing greater intimacy with family members, friends, neighbors, and even strangers (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004).

New Possibilities. It reflects the perception of positive self-changes and the discovery of new life opportunities following a potentially traumatic event.

Lindstrom, Cann, Calhoun, and Tedeschi (2013) suggest that cognitive reconstruction resulting from the traumatic event facilitates a better appreciation of life and subsequent changes in priorities. Consequently, trauma survivors may adopt healthier lifestyles, be more discerning in their choice of friends, and even completely alter their life goals.

Personal Strength. It involves a transformed self-perception where individuals feel more capable and resilient in overcoming difficulties. After confronting trauma, individuals often experience heightened feelings of personal resiliency, self-assurance, self-consciousness, acceptance, empathetic thinking, creativeness, maturity, self-respect, and competence in managing forthcoming difficulties. Trauma survivors develop an enhanced perception of their own

strength and fortitude.

Spiritual Change. It refers to the fortification of one's spiritual or religious faith, or a stronger belief than before, because of a possibly traumatic incident. Exposure to trauma or extreme adversities often leads individuals to experience an improvement in religious convictions and a stronger feeling of spiritual development. Strengthening of faith can improve their coping mechanisms, providing new avenues for life (Lindstrom et al., 2013). Consequently, victims feel an increased frequency of prayers, a heightened sense of gratitude to God, and a stronger faith.

Appreciation of Life. It involves valuing life and appreciating each day in a way that was not experienced before. It encompasses a heightened appreciation of existence and a reevaluation of life priorities, leading to significant life changes. Tedeschi and Calhoun (2004) opined that individuals who have experienced traumatic events often find themselves deeply contemplating thoughtful existential enquirers regarding their pre-trauma beliefs, deaths, and the significance of life. This reflective process leads to an enhanced comprehension of life's purpose and meaning.

Theoretical Frame Work

To support the relationship between street harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth among young women, the theoretical framework for this study includes a number of psychological theories and models.

Dyadic Power Theory (DPT) on Street Harassment

Dyadic Power Theory (DPT), a well-known theory about street harassment identifies the vertical relationship between the harasser and the victim. Harassers consider themselves more powerful and fearless and easily threaten others and no one can question them. They get this confidence because of the aimless support of society or physical and social advantages. On the other hand, victims are in constant fear and often feel powerless in confronting the perpetrator (DelGreco et al., 2020). This contrast brings distress for the victim and baseless sheer self-assurance for the harasser.

Regret Theory

This theory was established in 1982 by Graham Loomes and Robert Sugden.

According to this theory, regret occurs when individuals reflect on their decisions and perceive that deciding an alternative option would have resulted in an outcome that was better or when they experience negative results from their chosen option. This comparison can lead to regret and may influence future decision-making strategies to avoid similar feelings.

Decision Justification Theory

Decision justification theory (DJT) proposes that decision-related regret consists of two main elements: one involves the comparative or alternative assessment of the outcome, while the other pertains to the sense of self-blame for making a poor decision. The overall experience of regret over a choice at some point is influenced by only these two factors: Both the fact that the result is worse than some standard (often the outcome of the choice you chose to reject) and the fact that the decision you took was, in hindsight, unreasonable are regrets that you should feel (Connolly & Zeelenberg, 2002).

Post-Traumatic Growth Model

Post-traumatic growth is a concept that was first suggested by Tedeschi and Calhoun in 1995, often referred to as growing up in adversity, stress-related growth. It involves the idea of experiencing benefits or positive changes after a traumatic event.

The process starts with the occurrence of a traumatic event along with his negative consequences, which is highly distressing and disturbed an individual's fundamental beliefs (schemas) as well as goals, causing severe psychological distress. Assumptive beliefs are overall ideas about the world (such as the predictability, controllability, and benevolence of the world) that impact behavior. Trauma undermines the credibility of these beliefs, causing trauma survivors to question their thinking and their views of the world and their role in it.

Attempting to reconcile with the tragedy and reduce the associated suffering or distress, individuals often engage in automatic and unintentional ruminations about the trauma. As emotional distress diminishes, the process of

automatic rumination may evolve into deeper, intentional, and purposeful reflection about the ways in which the traumatic incident influenced the individual. Positive development is believed to occur when deliberate reflection is constructive and focused on discovering meaning, positive aspects, and reconsideration of the traumatic incident.

The Seismic Metaphor concept explains how traumatic situations act as "seismic" challenges that shatter, one's previous beliefs, objectives, convictions, and pre-trauma capabilities including their ability to handle emotional suffering (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 1995; 2004). The "seismic" metaphor compares the abruptness and intensity of how deeply held ideas are shattered to the effects of an earthquake, illustrating the rebuilding efforts individuals must undertake to reconstruct their shattered assumptive world after a traumatic event.

The intentional reflection (rumination) thought process phase enables persons who have undergone extremely traumatic circumstances to thoughtfully explore how they want to reconstruct their lives from scratch. So, by acknowledging the realness of their circumstances also recognizing their survival abilities, individuals may develop adaptive beliefs that enhance resilience and enable them to effectively face future challenges.

Through the process of integrating the positive transformations that take place into their own personal tales, individuals get an in-depth knowledge of their development in various significant ways. Victims of traumatic incidents realize that these challenging encounters could enhance their positive growth (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004).

Literature review

To find out the reliability of the current study, it is important to understand the connection between street harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth among young women, and also explore the previous literature that aligns with the findings of the current study. Street harassment, a pervasive issue, often leads to decision regret, where women doubt their choices, and blame themselves for adversities. By examining these variables together, the study provides insights into how these negative experiences might, paradoxically, foster positive

or constructive growth, and also highlights the complex nature of recovery and empowerment in the face of adversity.

A study done by Sarah and Daniel (2018) on survivors of multiple incidents such as street harassment incident victims, whether victims show post-traumatic growth or not after trauma, study reveals that encountering adversities might develop potential for positive development in victims from the negative consequences they face. Moreover, victims who survive such worse incidents constructively can face challenges more effectively in the future.

A study conducted by Rühle et al., (2024) on decision regret in medical settings illustrates that regret often arises from perceived negative outcomes and the impact of those outcomes on one's life.

Similarly, A research study conducted by Hickman et al., (2012) found that patients who receive an internal cardioverter defibrillator (ICD) may experience regret when the outcome of their decision is unfavorable. In the case of street harassment, women who experience such incidents may regret their decision to take a specific route that led them to the harassment. This regret is influenced by the traumatic nature of the harassment and the reflection on how their choice contributed to the negative experience. Additionally, Diotaiuti et al, (2022) demonstrated in the theory that regret is a relevant emotional response in various contexts. This highlights the theory's broader applicability in understanding how adverse experiences impact individuals' reflections and perceptions about decisions.

A study done by Zacchaeus (2020) explored the idea of post-traumatic growth (PTG) and how it used and changed people's perspective towards trauma in recent researches. Studies revealed that trauma survivors even from multiple backgrounds of terrible encounters including mental and physical harm can develop positive growth in the face of adversity and change the perspective that trauma could only lead to hinder growth also post-traumatic growth (PTG) reliable and valid measure of after trauma growth among survivors.

Study conducted by Fayaz, (2023) reviewed 22 studies on Post Traumatic Growth among women survivors of sexual assault, finding some levels of growth, especially in the "relating to

others" domain, suggesting that women who endure street harassment may also experience similar positive changes in their relationships and self-view.

A study conducted by Bryngeirsdottir et al., (2022) on female survivors of intimate partner violence (IPV) highlighted that post-traumatic growth enhances mental health and quality of life. This study predicts that adverse experiences could lead to positive outcomes, suggesting that such experiences may serve as a catalyst for personal growth.

Rationale

The bustling city streets, a troubling reality often unfolds for young women is "Street harassment". Street harassment was not merely an isolated incident but a pervasive, systemic issue that inflicted both psychological and physical harm on young women. Its normalization in society led to an alarming acceptance, society's dangerous acceptance of street harassment as an inevitable part of public life contributed to a cycle of self-blame and internalized oppression among victims.

The motivation behind this research stemmed from the need to challenge the normalization of street harassment and its devastating consequences on women's lives. The reason for conducting this study is to clarify the behaviors that constitute street harassment. Many women today may not recognize these actions due to the normalization of harassment in society. Behaviors ranging from seemingly minor acts like staring to extreme actions like public masturbation are all forms of street harassment that need to be identified and addressed.

Another reason is, that the effects of street harassment on young women have not been well studied in the context of what victims feel after the trauma. Victims of harassment sometimes start judging their actions and place unwarranted remorse on themselves, failing to see that they bear no responsibility for the abuse. Women often began to question their choices and worth, leading to decision regret as they grappled with the psychological burdens of harassment, which must be addressed and understood.

Furthermore, the purpose of the study was to investigate if there is a connection between these variables with positive growth, a positive transformation that can result from facing

traumatic experiences. Given a particular understanding of how trauma can lead to effective growth within women, it was the cue to divulge their internal suffering and contribute to viewing difficulties from a different perspective. Such reframing journeys usually end up viewing life from a different yet positive point and a strong relationship with internal growth and goals, resulting in empowering women to prosper despite difficulties in life

This research had remarkable ideas not limited to academic society but to a broader extent. By identifying the relationship between street harassment, regret of decisions, and post-traumatic growth, the research provides a wider understanding of the negative and positive psychological effects of trauma.

One of the most significant benefits of this research was its emphasis on post-traumatic growth which had not been recognized and given importance extensively under the topic of street harassment. The outcomes of this study were extremely significant in discovering new way of involvement and support for victims. From this information, the educational workshops and awareness sessions could be updated for the reduction of street harassment and its disturbing impact on young women helping them rebuild themselves with power and reliability after undergoing traumatic experiences.

Hypotheses

- H1: There is likely to be a positive relationship between street harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth.
- H2: Street harassment and decision regret positively predict post-traumatic growth among young women.

Method

The research wants to investigate a link between street Harassment, self Objectification, decision

regret, and post-traumatic growth among young women.

Research design

Correlational research design means to determine the relationship among two or more variables (Cresswell, 2012). The correlational research design was used to find the relations between street Harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth among young women.

Sample

The target population of this study was only young women. The data was collected from 250 young women between the ages of 19 to 35. Purposive sampling strategy, a type of non-probability sampling, involves the researcher purposely selecting participants based on research criteria (American Psychological Association, 2018). The sample strategy used by the researcher was non-probability purposive sampling.

Inclusion & Exclusion criteria

- Young women aged 19 to 35 years were included in this study.
- Women who had encountered street harassment at least once in their lives were included.
- Only women who were at least graduates were included.
- Participants with mental illness or disabilities were excluded.

Demographic information sheet

The researcher devised a demographic questionnaire to gather biographical information from the study participants. The demographic information sheet included various characteristics of the participants, such as age, gender (men/women), education, socioeconomic status (upper class, upper middle class, middle class, lower class, lower middle class).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of Demographic Variable (N = 200)

Demographic	Characteristic	N	(%)	M	SD
Age				23.36	4.04
Gender					
Female		250	100.0		
Education					
BS		141	56.4		
MS		45	18.0		

BSc	23	9.2
MSc	23	9.2
M.Phil	18	7.2
Social-economic status		
Upper class	25	10.0
Upper Middle class	81	32.4
Middle Class	103	41.2
Lower Class	20	8.0
Lower Middle Class	21	8.4

Note. n = Frequency; % = Percentage

Operational definition

Street Harassment

“Street harassment is a form of harassment, primarily sexual harassment that consists of unwanted sexualized comments, provocative gestures, honking, wolf whistlings, indecent exposures, stalking, persistent sexual advances, and touching by strangers, in public areas such as streets, shopping malls, and public transportation” (Whittaker & Kowalski, 2014).

Decision regret

“Distress or remorse after a (health care) decision” (Brehaut, 2003).

Post-traumatic growth

“Post-traumatic growth also known as growing up in adversity is the term used to describe the positive psychological growth, that happens as a consequence of surviving with trauma or extremely challenging life circumstances. These phenomena should be seen not as an alternative, but as a parallel process in relation to adverse psychological effects” (Tedeschi et al., 2018).

Assessment measure

- The Mexican Sexual Street Harassment Questionnaire (MSSHQ).
- Decision Regret Scale (DRS).
- Post Traumatic Growth Inventory (PTGI).

The Mexican Sexual Street Harassment Questionnaire (MSSHQ)

The Mexican Sexual Street Harassment Questionnaire assesses foam of street harassment. These items together account for 58.53% of the variance, with a total α value of 0.92. Participants indicate their scores on a 5-point Likert scale where: 1 implies-It has never

happened to me to 5 implies - It has happened to me very frequently in the last year (Gurrola-Peña et al., 2022).

Decision regret scale (DRS)

A 5-item scale ranging from (1) *strongly agree* to (5) *strongly disagree* refers to measuring feelings of remorse, self-blame, or the belief that a better alternative could have been chosen. Regret is quantified at a certain moment when the response is able to think about the consequences of such a choice. Psychometric testing studies with several applications showed an Alpha Coefficient: of $\alpha = 0.92$, (Brehaut, 2003) and in non-clinical settings scale showed an Alpha Coefficient: of $\alpha = 0.81$ (Diotaiuti et al., 2022b).

Post-traumatic growth inventory (PTGI)

According to Tedeschi and Calhoun (1996), the post-traumatic growth inventory is a tool used to assess the degree of post-traumatic development in individuals who have survived a traumatic incident. It has twenty-one items. Participants indicate their scores on a 6-point Likert scale where: 0 implies - *I did not experience this as a result of my crisis* to 5 implies - *I experienced this change to a very great degree as a result of my crisis*. Using a scale range, participants are asked to identify the extent to which they have or have not experienced a certain change. The reliability of the whole scale was $\alpha = 0.98$.

Procedure

The research process began with the selection of the topic of study from various sub-domains of psychology, which was subsequently approved by the supervisor.

Permission was obtained from the original

authors to use the relevant scales. A factual basis for the study was established with the support of relevant literature. Following successful results from a pilot study involving 20 participants, the research was expanded to include 250 young women, with the target population being personally approached for data collection. After data collection, analysis was run in SPSS to find relationships between variables. Throughout the research process, ethical guidelines were adhered to, and APA guidelines were meticulously followed in finalizing the results.

Ethical consideration

- Topic approval from supervisor and psychology department, University of Management and Technology, Lahore.
- Permission was taken for the use of scale by the authors.
- Informed consent was given to the

participant prior to filling out the survey.

- The participants were briefed about the nature of the study.
- They were informed that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential.
- They had the right to leave the research at any moment.
- Honest reporting of the result was carried out.

Results

The findings chapter examined the correlations between the study variables, provided the psychometric properties of the research measures, provided visual representations through tables, and offered a summary of the results, giving a comprehensive overview of the data and its implications within the context of the research.

Table 2

Psychometric Properties for Scales

Scales	M	SD	Range	Cronbach's α
Street harassment	48.1	15.1	18-77	.90
Decision regret	19.1	4.0	8-25	.70
Post-traumatic growth	54.6	12.9	25-78	.91

Note. SD = Standard Deviation, M = Mean, α = Cronbach's Alpha,

The table presents the psychometric analysis of the scales used in the current investigation. The Cronbach's alpha for the street harassment scale was .903, which suggests a high level of internal consistency. The decision regret scale had a

Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .703, which also suggests satisfactory internal consistency. Eventually, the post-traumatic growth scale reached a Cronbach's alpha of .919, indicating excellent internal consistency (DATA tab, 2024).

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation between the Variable of Interest

Variable	n	M	SD	1	2	3
1. Street harassment	250	48.19	15.16	-		
2. Decision regret	250	19.13	4.03	.63**	-	
3. Post-traumatic growth	250	54.63	12.94	.81**	.47**	-

*p<05. **p < .01. ***p < .001.

The research identified significant positive relationships among the variables of interest. Street harassment and post-traumatic growth are strongly

positively correlated, with a correlation ($r = .81$, $p < 0.01$). Furthermore, there is a significant positive relationship between street harassment and

decision regret ($r = .63, p < 0.01$). The is a moderate positive

significant relation between decision regret and post-traumatic growth ($r = .47, p < 0.01$).

Table 4

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Post-Traumatic Growth

Variables	B	SE	T	p	95%CI
Constant	11.52	5.63	2.04	.042	[0.42, 22.62]
Street harassment	0.61	0.04	13.79	.000	[0.52, 0.69]
Decision regret	1.50	0.18	8.38	.000	[1.15, 1.86]

Note. N = 250

The regression model explains 67.1% of the variance in post-traumatic growth. The F-value of 137.8 indicates a significant overall fit. Beta coefficients show that street harassment ($\beta = 0.717, p < .001$) and decision regret ($\beta = 0.470, p < .001$) have positive effects on post-traumatic growth making a significant contribution.

Summary of results

- The results show that street harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth are all significantly positively correlated.
- Regression analysis reveals that street harassment and decision regret strongly predict post-traumatic growth. The model explains 67.1% of the variance in post-traumatic growth, indicating a strong overall fit.

Discussion

The discussion chapter explains the factual basis and outcome obtained from this research. This study was conducted to explore the relationship among street harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth in young women. Additionally, this study aimed to identify the prediction of these variables on post-traumatic growth.

People often perceive trauma as having solely negative consequences; however, recent researches on trauma, including the present study, reveals that traumatic experiences and their negative consequences such as street harassment and decision regret could result in post-traumatic growth (PTG). A study conducted by Zięba et al., (2019) indicates that the trauma narratives frequently show increased personal strength, enhanced relationships, and a deeper appreciation for life, suggesting that trauma, such as street

harassment, can foster substantial personal development.

The relationship between street harassment and decision regret in the current study, particularly in non-clinical settings, presents a unique application of decision regret, and there is no existing literature on it in non-clinical settings. Traditional decision regret researches often examines clinical or high-stakes environments where decisions with significant life implications can lead to regret over negative outcomes. Similarly, decision regret after street harassment arises from the negative outcome of the incident.

The positive relationship between decision regret and post-traumatic growth provides a factual basis that decision regret, arising from the negative outcome of a choice an individual made reflecting on choices can prompt individuals to reassess and adjust their life strategies and values. This reflective process, can foster personal development and improvement. Because, regret is linked to the idea of a mistake made or an opportunity missed, provoking the desire to correct and resolve the situation (Inman & Zeelenberg, 2002). These findings also align with Tedeschi and Calhoun's (2004) theory of post-traumatic growth.

The current study suggests that street harassment and decision regret positively predict post-traumatic growth among young women. Research supports this by showing that trauma, despite its negative impact, can lead to significant personal growth. A study conducted by Isgandarova (2023) found that women who endured genocidal rape during the war often experience post-traumatic growth, finding new meaning in life through spirituality and support

systems. This finding predicts that women who face severe trauma, such as street harassment, might similarly experience growth through the development of new perspectives and support mechanisms.

Similarly, A study conducted by Guggisberg et al., (2021) found that survivors of sexual violence can experience post-traumatic growth by engaging in self- reflection and altruistic actions.

Decision regret, which stems from reflecting on choices that result in negative outcomes, can be a powerful catalyst for growth. It compels individuals to reassess their life decisions and strategies, driving them to make more constructive choices in the future. This reflective process, when managed positively, can lead to significant personal development and contribute to post-traumatic growth by encouraging a renewed sense of purpose and direction.

Post-Traumatic Growth (PTG) has gained attention in the past two decades for its insights into how individuals respond to trauma. Research on post-traumatic growth (PTG) related to street harassment and decision regret is still limited, partly due to the unique nature of these variables. While specific studies on street harassment are sparse, research on other types of trauma provides a framework for understanding potential growth in this context. Similarly, existing literature on decision regret offers relevant insights. However, further research is required to investigate these relationships across more diverse contexts.

Conclusion

The current study investigates the interplay between street harassment, decision regret, and post-traumatic growth among young women. The research indicate that although street harassment is a terrible experience and posits negative effects on young women such as decision regret the stress victims go through could lead them to post-traumatic growth because of the reflection process which takes individuals to reassess their beliefs and life decisions, although triggered by trauma and its negative consequences can lead to significant personal development in the face of difficulty.

By taking this as an opportunity to grow many victims move forward in there life with renewed strength.

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